

Personal Therapy: Towards Sustainability and Capacity Building among Workers in Organisations in Kenya

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Abstract

The growth and success of all organizations, depend on the health of their workers; both the physical and mental health. The counselor plays a great role in ensuring that workers enjoy good mental health through facilitation of their self awareness and life skill acquisition. However, counselor may sometimes be overwhelmed with his/her own personal concerns to the extent his/her functioning is curtailed. By becoming clients themselves, counselors gain an inner steadiness that increases their ability to help others. In learning self-acceptance and patience through personal therapy, counselors will find it easier to be patient with clients and to respect each individual's unique process and pacing. Personal therapy helps counselors learn patience and calmness in the unpredictable waters of an organization. Without personal therapy, counselors are more susceptible to acting prematurely and subverting the difficult and fallow periods so crucial to therapeutic progress. Personal therapy is a core component of counselor self-care, which is another means of preventing client harm and enhancing his/her personal sustainability and capacity building. The study adopted the content analysis research design. Content analysis is a research technique used to make replicable and valid inferences by interpreting and coding textual material. By systematically evaluating texts qualitative data can be converted into quantitative data. Content analysis is valuable in organizational research because it allows researchers to recover and examine the nuances of organizational behaviors, stakeholder perceptions, and societal trends. It is also an important bridge between purely quantitative and purely qualitative research methods. Research findings showed that workers who are mentally health are dedicated to work, highly motivated and have high stamina for work. This status facilitates high organizational returns. The three major determinants of organizational behavior are the people, the organizational structure, and the technology involved. People come to the workplace with social, physiological as well as psychological needs which the organization must fulfill in order to avoid being demoralized. When workers lack motivation they tend to resort to anti-work behaviors which impact negatively on the work performance and credibility of an organization. Personal therapy prepares the counselor to effectively tackle these workplace challenges.

Keywords: Personal Therapy, sustainability, Capacity Building, Empowerment, Motivation.

INTRODUCTION

The growth and success of all organizations depend on the health of their workers both physical and mental health. Recognizing and promoting mental health is an essential part of creating a safe and healthy workplace. There are several key issues shown to have a significant effort on employee mental health. Within each key issue are various factors that organizations need to consider in their efforts to create a mentally healthy workplace. Issues affecting employee mental health fall under one or multiple psychosocial risk factors. The psychosocial risk factors impact negatively on the organizational health, the health of the individual employees and financial bottom line including the way work is carried out and the context in which work occurs.

Sustainability and capacity building among workers in the organization determines the growth of the organization. This facilitates attachment, job commitment, job satisfaction, job involvement, positive work moods, desire to remain with the organization such will translate to high level work output among workers.

The counselor plays a great role in ensuring that workers enjoy good mental health through facilitation of their self awareness and life skill acquisition. However, the counselor may sometimes be overwhelmed with his/her own personal concerns to the extent that his/her functioning is curtailed. The counselor is impacted by the clients' concerns. Therapeutic terms like transference and

counter transference often surface in therapeutic relationship they engage in. It has been said that "All therapist are wounded healers" If therapists are in fact wounded healers, where are they able to address their wounds and needs? Personal therapy for therapist becomes a source of healing. Personal therapy helps counselors learn patience and calmness in the unpredictable waters of an organization; without personal therapy, counselors are more susceptible to acting prematurely and subverting the difficult and fallow periods so crucial to therapeutic progress. Personal therapy is a core component of counselor self-care, which is another means of preventing client harm and enhancing his/her personal sustainability and capacity building for greater work output

The study adopted content analysis research design and the objectives were:

1. To determine the role of personal therapy on counselors mental wellness and competence
2. To investigate the relationship between the therapist psychological wellness and clients wellness(workers wellness)
3. To explore the workers psychological needs and overall work output
4. To find out the workers mental wellness ,sustainability and capacity building

Research Methodology

The study adopted the content analysis research design. Content analysis is a research technique used to make replicable and valid inferences by interpreting and coding textual material. By systematically evaluating texts qualitative data can be converted into quantitative data. Content analysis is valuable in organizational research because it allows researchers to recover and examine the nuances of organizational behaviors, stakeholder perceptions, and societal trends. It is also an important bridge between purely quantitative and purely qualitative research methods. In one regard, content analysis allows researchers to analyze socio-cognitive and perceptual constructs that are difficult to study via traditional quantitative archival methods. At the same time, it allows researchers to gather large samples that may be difficult to employ in purely qualitative

studies (Duriau *et al.*, 2007). This study reviewed literature from parts of the world including Canada, Australia, Britain, USA and Africa. Analysis was made on experiences of workers in the workplace as well as those of workplace counselors. Conclusions were made exclusively from content analysis.

Results and Discussion

Workers Psychological Needs and Overall Work Output

Workers' output in the workplace is largely influenced by the organizational structure. Although we tend to think of organizations in their collective sense, they are of course comprised of individual human beings. These individuals act out their working lives within the framework of an organizations structure and in context of a particular organization's culture.

Studies on people on small groups and as individuals have shown that differences between individuals are as important as the common features. An individual at work is perceived by others as a physical person personal with a range of abilities and as a personality (Cole, 1995). There are several issues shown to have a significant effect on employee mental health within each key issue are various factors that organizations need to consider in their efforts to create a mentally healthy workplace. Issues affecting employee mental health fall under one of *Multiple Psychosocial Risk (PSR)* factors.

Thirteen psychosocial risk (PSR) factors have been identified by researchers at Simon Fraser University "based on extensive research and review of empirical data from national and international best practices. The factors were also determined based on existing and emerging Canadian case law and legislation." http://www.ccohs.ca/oshanswers/psychosocial/mentalhealth_risk.html. The 13 organizational factors that impact organizational health, the health of individual employees and the financial bottom line, including the way work is carried out and the context in which work occurs (http://www.ccohs.ca/oshanswers/psychosocial/mentalhealth_risk.html).

Psychosocial Risk (PSR) Factors Identified By Researchers at Simon Fraser University

Psychological Support

A workplace where co-workers and supervisors are supportive of employees' psychological and mental health concerns, and respond appropriately as needed. For some organizations, the most important aspect of psychological support may be to protect against traumatic stressors at work. Employee perceptions of a lack of psychological support from their organization can lead to: increased absenteeism, withdrawal behaviours, conflict and strain which can lead to fatigue, headaches, burnout and anxiety, turnover, loss of productivity, increased costs, greater risk of accidents and incidents and injuries.

Organizational Culture

Culture "sets the tone" for an organization - a negative culture can undermine the effectiveness of the best programs, policies and services intended to support the workforce. An unhealthy culture creates more stress, which lowers employee well-being. A culture of "profit at all costs" and constant chaotic urgency can create an environment in which burnout is the norm.

Clear Leadership & Expectations

A workplace where there is effective leadership and support that helps employees know what they need to do, how their work contributes to the organization and whether there are impending changes. Leaders who are more "instrumental" in their approach (focusing on producing outcomes, with little attention paid to the "big picture," the psychosocial within the organization, and the individual employees) are more likely to hear staff health complaints including general feelings of malaise, irritability and nervousness. Similarly, leaders who do not demonstrate visible concern for their own physical and psychological health set a negative example for their staff and can undermine the legitimacy of any organizational program, policy and/or service intended to support employees. Middle managers are at greater risk because they must be leaders and be led simultaneously. This role conflict can lead to feelings of powerlessness and stress.

Civility and Respect

A workplace where employees are respectful and considerate in their interactions with one

another, as well as with customers, clients and the public is seen to be observing civility. Civility and respect are based on showing esteem, care and consideration for others, and acknowledging their dignity. A workplace that lacks civility and respect can lead to emotional exhaustion amongst staff, greater conflicts, and job withdrawal. A work environment that is uncivil and disrespectful also exposes organizations to the threat of more grievances and legal risks.

One example of disrespectful behaviour is bullying. Exposure to workplace bullying is associated with psychological complaints, depression, burnout, anxiety, aggression, psychosomatic complaints and musculoskeletal health complaints. Bullying not only affects those directly involved, but also affects bystanders, as they too experience higher levels of stress. A number of provinces currently have legislation to address such behaviours.

Psychological Competencies & Requirements

A workplace where there is a good fit between employees' interpersonal and emotional competencies, their job skills and the position they hold. A good fit means that the employees possess the technical skills and knowledge for a particular position as well as the psychological skills and emotional intelligence (self-awareness, impulse control, persistence, self-motivation, empathy and social deftness) to do the job. Note that a subjective job fit (when employees feel they fit their job) can be more important than an objective job fit (when the employee is assessed and matched to the job).

A good job fit is associated with the following characteristics; fewer health complaints, lower levels of depression, greater self-esteem, a more positive self-concept, enhanced performance, job satisfaction and employee retention.

When there is a poor job fit, employees can experience job strain, which can be expressed as emotional distress and provocation, excessive dwelling on thoughts, defensiveness, energy depletion and lower mood levels. Organizationally, job misfit is linked to fewer applicants in the recruitment and training process, lack of enjoyment and engagement, poor productivity, conflict, and greater voluntary turnover.

Growth & Development

A workplace where employees receive encouragement and support in the development of their interpersonal, emotional and job skills, they have a propensity for growth. This type of workplace provides a range of internal and external opportunities for employees to build their repertoire of competencies. It helps employees with their current jobs as well as prepares them for possible future positions. Employees who are not challenged by their work will grow bored, their well-being will suffer, and their performance will drop. When staff do not have opportunities to learn and improve their interpersonal and psychological skills, the result can be conflict, disengagement and distress.

Recognition and Reward

A workplace where there is appropriate acknowledgement and appreciation of employees' efforts in a fair and timely manner. This includes appropriate and regular financial compensation as well as employee or team celebrations, recognition of years served, and/or milestones reached. Recognition and reward results in the following benefits; motivation for employees, fuels the desire to excel, builds self-esteem, encourages employees to exceed expectations and enhances team success. Employees receiving appropriate recognition and reward have more energy and enthusiasm, a greater sense of pride and participation in their work, and are more likely to treat colleagues and customers with courtesy, respect and understanding.

Lack of recognition and reward undermines employee confidence in their work and trust in the organization. Employees may feel demoralized or they may quit. An imbalance between effort and reward is a significant contributor to burnout and emotional distress leading to a range of psychological and physical disorders.

Involvement and Influence

When employees feel they have meaningful input into their work they are more likely to be engaged, to have higher morale, and to take pride in their organization. This, in turn, increases the willingness to make extra effort when required. Job involvement is associated with increased psychological well-being,

enhanced innovation, and organizational commitment.

If employees do not believe they have a voice in the affairs of the organization, they tend to feel a sense of indifference or helplessness. Job alienation or non-involvement is associated with cynicism and distress, greater turnover, and burnout.

Workload Management

Most employees willingly work hard and feel a "good day's work" is fulfilling and rewarding. Workload management is important because there is a unique relationship between job demands, intellectual demands and job satisfaction. Job demands reduce job satisfaction, while intellectual demands or decision-making latitude, increase job satisfaction. Even when there are high demands, if employees also have high decision-making ability, they will be able to thrive. Having high decision-making latitude also allows for positive coping behaviours to be learned and experienced.

Any system subject to excess load without reprieve will break. This is as true for people as it is for equipment. Increased demands, without opportunities for control, result in physical, psychological and emotional fatigue, and increase stress and strain. Emotionally fatigued individuals also have a diminished sense of personal accomplishment and an increased sense of inadequacy. Excessive workload is one of the main reasons employees are negative about their jobs and their employers.

Engagement

Employees enjoy and feel connected to their work and where they feel motivated to do their job well. Employee engagement can be physical (energy exerted), emotional (positive job outlook and passionate about their work) or cognitive (devote more attention to their work and be absorbed in their job). Engaged employees feel connected to their work because they can relate to, and are committed to, the overall success and mission of their company. Engagement is similar to, but should not be mistaken for job satisfaction, job involvement, organizational commitment, psychological empowerment, and intrinsic motivation.

Engagement is important for individual satisfaction and psychological health, and leads to: increased profitability for company,

greater customer satisfaction, enhanced task performance, greater morale, greater motivation, increased organizational citizenship behaviours (behaviours of personal choice that benefit the organization). Organizations that do not promote engagement experience several problems including; negative economic impact in productivity losses, psychological and medical consequences, have greater employee turnover, workplace deviance (in the form of withholding effort), counterproductive behavior and withdrawal behaviours.

Balance

Present in a workplace where there is recognition of the need for balance between the demands of work, family and personal life. This factor reflects the fact that everyone has multiple roles employees, parents, partners, etc. These multiple roles can be enriching and allow for fulfillment of individual strengths and responsibilities, but conflicting responsibilities can lead to role conflict or overload. Greater workplace flexibility enables employees to minimize work-life conflict by allowing them to accomplish the tasks necessary in their daily lives.

Work-life balance is a state of well-being that allows a person to effectively manage multiple responsibilities at work, at home and in their community. Work-life balance is different for everyone and it supports physical, emotional, family and community health and does so without grief, stress or negative impact. Recognizing the need for work-life balance enhances workers psychological stability. The workers therefore experience positive work values. Such employees feel valued and happier both at work and at home, reduced stress, maintained concentration, confidence, responsibility, and sense of control at work. Work-life balance leads to enhanced employee well-being, commitment, job satisfaction, organizational citizenship behaviours (behaviours of personal choice that benefit the organization), job performance and reduced stress

When work-family role conflict occurs (that is, roles within the workplace and outside it are overwhelming to a person or interfering with one another), health and well-being are undermined by accumulating home and job stress. This imbalance can lead to such issues as: constant tiredness, bad temper, inability to progress, high job stress resulting in

dissatisfaction with work and being absent either physically or mentally. These effects can then lead to additional stress-related illness, as well as higher cholesterol, depressive symptoms, and overall decreased health. The impact on the organization can include increased costs due to benefit payouts, absenteeism, disability, and turnover.

Not all employees will have the same work-life balance issues. Age, cultural, gender, family and marital status, care-giver demands, socioeconomic status and many other factors affect an employee's work-life balance. Organizations will benefit from having flexible arrangements to address this issue.

Psychological Protection

Workplace psychological safety is demonstrated when employees feel able to put themselves on the line, ask questions, seek feedback, report mistakes and problems, or propose a new idea without fearing negative consequences to themselves, their job or their career. A psychologically safe and healthy workplace actively promotes emotional well-being among employees while taking all reasonable steps to minimize threats to employee mental health.

When employees are psychologically protected they demonstrate greater job satisfaction, enhanced team learning behaviour and improved performance. Employees are more likely to speak up and become involved. They show increased morale and engagement and are less likely to experience stress-related illness. Psychologically protected workplaces also experience fewer grievances, conflicts and liability risks. When employees are not psychologically safe, they experience demoralization, a sense of threat, disengagement, and strain. They perceive workplace conditions as ambiguous and unpredictable. This can, in turn, undermine shareholder, consumer, and public confidence in the organization.

Protection of Physical Safety

This factor includes the work environment itself. Steps can be taken by management to protect the physical safety of employees. Examples include policies, training, appropriate response to incidents or situations identified as risks, and a demonstrated

concern for employees' physical safety. Employees who work in an environment that is perceived as physically safe will feel more secure and engaged. Higher levels in the confidence of the safety protection at work results in lower rates of psychological distress and mental health issues. Safety is enhanced through minimizing hazards, training, response to incidents, and the opportunity to have meaningful input into the workplace policies and practices. The concept of 'safety climate' is linked to this factor as they both relate to the larger culture or climate of the organization.

Failure to protect physical safety results in workplaces that are likely to be more dangerous. Not only could employees be injured or develop illnesses, those who do not see their workplace as physically safe will feel less secure and less engaged. The team of researchers at Simon Fraser University identified several other key issues in the workplace that affect employee mental health. Within each issue are various factors that organizations need to consider in their efforts to create a mentally healthy workplace.

Stigma and Discrimination - Stigma is a personal attitude and belief that negatively labels a group of people, such as those with mental illness. Stigma creates fear and consequently results in discrimination which discourages individuals and their families from getting the help they need.

Stress - Stress refers to potentially negative physical or mental tensions experienced by a person. A **stressor** is any event or situation that an individual perceives as a threat; precipitates either adaptation or the stress response. Stress can come from both good and bad experiences, so the effects of stress can be positive or negative. Stress is not all bad - without stress, there would be no productivity or engagement. Stress becomes a problem when individuals are not able to handle an event or situation and become overwhelmed.

Demand/control and effort/reward relationships - Major causes of job stress come from problems with conflicts in **demand vs. control** as well as **effort vs. reward**. When the demand and control an employee has at work changes, stress results if either factor is not increased or decreased proportionately. The

same is true for the relationship between effort and reward. Changes to the organization can make for a more mentally healthy workplace, especially when employees feel appropriately rewarded for their effort and in control of their work.

Presenteeism - Presenteeism is the action of employees coming to work despite having a sickness that justifies an absence, therefore they are performing their work under sub-optimal conditions. When employees come to work not mentally present due to an illness, extreme family/life pressures or stress, they are not giving themselves adequate time to get better. Presenteeism can occur because employees feel they cannot afford to take the day off, there is no back-up plan for tasks the individual is responsible for, when they return to work, there would be even more to do, committed to personally attending meetings or events, concerned about job insecurity related to downsizing or restructuring.

Job Burnout - Job burnout is a state of physical, emotional and mental exhaustion caused by long-term exposure to demanding work situations. Burnout is the cumulative result of stress. Anyone can experience job burnout. However, professions with high job demands and few supports can increase the prevalence of burnout and reduce engagement. Helping professions, such as jobs in health care, teaching or counseling, often have high rates of burnout.

Burnout has three main characteristics:

1. exhaustion (i.e. the depletion or draining of mental resources)
2. cynicism (i.e. indifference or a distant attitude towards one's job)
3. lack of professional efficacy (i.e. the tendency to evaluate one's work performance negatively, resulting in feelings of insufficiency and poor job-related self-esteem)

Harassment, Violence, Bullying and Mobbing - Most people think of violence as a physical assault. However, workplace violence is a much broader problem. It is any act in which a person is abused, threatened, intimidated or assaulted in his or her employment. Workplace violence includes:

threatening behaviour- such as shaking fists, destroying property or throwing objects, verbal or written threats - any expression of an intent to inflict, harm, harassment; any behaviour that demeans, embarrasses, humiliates, annoys, alarms or verbally abuses a person and that is known or would be expected to be unwelcome. This includes words, gestures, intimidation, bullying, or other inappropriate activities. Verbal abuse consists of swearing, insults or condescending language, physical attacks- hitting, shoving, pushing or kicking, bullying- repeated, unreasonable or inappropriate behaviour directed towards an employee (or group of employees) that creates a risk to health and safety, mobbing - ongoing, systematic bullying of an individual by his or her co-workers - this includes rudeness and physical intimidation, as well as more subtle and possibly unintentional behaviour involving social ostracism and exclusion.

Many provincial occupational health and safety acts have been expanded to include harm to psychological well-being. Organizations should not tolerate any violent behaviour including aggression, harassment or threats of violence. Violent or aggressive behaviour hurts the mental health of everyone in the organization and creates a psychologically unsafe work environment filled with fear and anxiety.

Substance Use, Misuse and Abuse at Work -

Substance use, misuse, abuse and coping strategies can have a significant impact on mental health at work. Addictions and mental health conditions are often coupled (called a concurrent disorder). However, it is often the addiction that first gets noticed, especially in the workplace. Generally, substance use becomes a problem when an individual has lost control over their use and/or continues to use despite experiencing negative consequences. Employers should look for warning signs that indicate an employee may be struggling with substance abuse. Some signs of substance abuse are similar to those caused by increased stress, lack of sleep and physical or mental illness. Don't assume that an employee has a substance abuse problem; however, ignoring warning signs will only worsen the problem. Mental illness is more prevalent than many people realize.

A study carried out by LaMontagne, Keegel and Vallance (2007) revealed that around 45%

of Australians aged between 16 and 85 will experience a mental illness at some point in their life, while one in five Australian adults will experience a mental illness in any given year the problem becomes worse if someone is indeed struggling. Despite one in five Australians experiencing mental health problems each year, nearly half of all senior managers believe none of their workers will experience a mental health problem at work.

A research carried out in South Africa by (Hamdulay, 2013) showed that Mental illness in the workplace leads to decreased productivity, increased sick-related absenteeism, poor work quality, wasted materials and even compromised workplace safety. Despite the significant financial loss to employers and broad economy, many mental disorders fly below the radar in the workplace. A more proactive approach for managing mental illness in the workplace is a strategic imperative for South African employers. The South African Association of Social Workers in Private Practice estimates that 50% of workplace accidents are related to substance abuse. An undetected substance abuser can cost the employer 25% of that person's wages. However, in many workplaces, employees choose to suffer their mental illness in silence, fearing stigma should they speak out, while employers avoid asking too many questions, hoping mental health disorders will just disappear on their own. Nevertheless, the latest Council for Medical Schemes (CMS) Report 2013-14 confirms that the prevalence of mental illness amongst medical schemes beneficiaries is rising. Total benefits per average (Hamdulay, 2013) beneficiary per month (pabpm) paid to psychiatrists increased by nearly 35% from 2011 to 2013. The total benefits paid to psychologists pabpm increased by 26% from 2011 to 2013, while the total benefits paid pabpm to mental health institutions from 2011 to 2013 increased by 58%.

The latest CMS data also shows that treatment for bipolar mood disorder (BMD) - a Prescribed Minimum Benefits condition and one of the top chronic conditions - increased by 173% from 2007 to 2012. Mental health problems cost employers in the UK £30 billion a year through lost production, recruitment and absence - so why aren't we doing more about it?

Relationship between the Therapist Psychological Wellness and Client's Wellness

However, counselor may sometimes be overwhelmed with his/her own personal concerns to the extent his/her functioning is curtailed. How can counselors understand what they are asking of clients unless these counselors have undergone their own therapy? Sitting in the client's chair weekly – experiencing exactly what it is like to be the client – would greatly increase beginner counselors' empathy.

No other aspect of counselor education provides this firsthand knowledge of the client experience: the frustrations, the successes, the challenges. Counselors who have participated in their own personal therapy will have greater empathy for their clients because they have been there. By becoming clients themselves, counselors gain an inner steadiness that increases their ability to help others. In learning self-acceptance and patience through personal therapy, counselors will find it easier to be patient with clients and to respect each individual's unique process and pacing. Personal therapy helps counselors learn patience and calmness in the unpredictable waters of an organization.

Without personal therapy, counselors are more susceptible to acting prematurely and subverting the difficult and fallow periods so crucial to therapeutic progress. Personal therapy is a core component of counselor self-care, which is another means of preventing client harm and enhancing his/her personal sustainability and capacity building.

The Role of Personal Therapy on Counselor's Mental Wellness and Competence

Among the many factors that influence a counselors abilities personal therapy is the most crucial. Psychologist have called personal therapy I turning of the *"therapist most valuable instrument- the Therapists own Self."*

Counselors who have participated in their own personal therapy will have greater empathy for their clients because they have been there.

Personal therapy achieves a lot for the therapist. These include such benefits as; Increasing empathy, Increasing patience and tolerance of uncertainty, Facilitating therapy,

Preventing client harm through self knowledge, Preventing client harm through self care and decreasing the stigma of psychotherapy *"If you are gasping for air you cannot help other people"* says Rankin, Psychologist from Walden University. Counselors who neglect their own, mental, physical and spiritual self care eventually run out of oxygen and cannot effectively help their clients because all of their energy is going out to the clients and nothing is coming back in to replenish the counselor's energy. Wellness is one of the critical factors in being healthy counselors.

Workers' Mental-Wellness, Sustainability and Capacity Building.

Mental health problems affect many employees- a fact that is usually overlooked because these disorders tend to be hidden at work. Employees may be reluctant to seek treatment because of the stigma attached to having a psychiatric disorder out of fear that they might jeopardize their jobs. As a result mental health disorder often goes unrecognized and untreated not only damaging an individual's health and career, but also reducing productivity at work.

In one study examining the financial impact of 25 chronic physical and mental health problems, when researchers ranked the most costly health conditions, depression ranked first and anxiety ranked fifth; with obesity, arthritis and back and neck pain in between. Mental health problems considerably increase the risk of leaving employment compared to other health problems (Burchardt, 2003). Over the past 10 years, the proportion of all claimants of incapacity benefits who are claiming because of mental health problems has risen from 26% to 40% and it has overtaken musculoskeletal disorders as the commonest cause. This has happened because whilst the total number of new claimants has fallen, the number with mental Health.

Many of the studies in the field have concluded that the indirect costs of mental health disorders particularly, lost productivity, exceed companies spending on direct costs such as health insurance contribution and pharmacy expenses. Researchers suggest that companies should invest in the mental health of workers not only for the sake of the employees but to improve own bottom line. Most of the research on the costs benefits of treatment has been done on

employees with depression. The studies have found out that when depression is adequately treated, companies reduce job-related accidents, sick days and employee turnover, as well as improve the number of hours worked and employee productivity

Before workers go down with depression, they would have sessions with the workplace counselor hence the mental wellness of the counselor would determine mental wellness of the client.

Conclusion

The literature on the mental health problems in the workplace suggest that personal toll on employees and the financial cost to companies could be eased if a greater proportion of workers who need treatment were able to receive it. Before workers plunge into work-related mental health problems, the workplace counselor should be engaged to enhance workers self-awareness and self understanding; such would revitalize workers' energy and stamina to work hence a higher work output.

REFERENCES

- Burchardt, T. (2003) Employment retention and the onset of sickness or disability: Evidence from labour force survey longitudinal datasets. *London: Department for Work and Pensions. Burns,*
- Duriau, Reger, & Pfarrer, (2007). A Content Analysis of the Content Analysis Literature in Organization Studies: *Research Themes, Data Sources, and Methodological Refinements. Organization Research Methods, 10: 5-34.*
- Fraenkel, J. R., Wallen, N. E. & Hyun, H. H. (2012) How to Design and Evaluate Research in Education, *San Francisco State University, ISBN: 0078097851*
- Whiteford, Sheridan, Cleary, Chant, Wang, Kessler (2008). The Prevalence of Psychological Distress in Employees and Associated Occupational Risk Factors, Hilton, LaMontagne A.D, Keegel T & Vallance, D. (2007) Protecting and Promoting Mental Health in the Workplace: *Developing a Systems Approach to Job Stress, Health Promotion Journal of Australia 2007, 18, 221-8*
- Marmot, M., Siegrist J. & Theorell, T. (2006) *Health and the Psychological Environment at Work, Social Determinants of Health 2006, 97-130*
- Comcare (2005). Working Well, An

Organisational Approach to Preventing Psychological Injury, A guide for Corporate, HR and OHS Managers, as cited at Australian Public Service (2006)

Harris M. F, Silove, D, Kehag E, Barratt A, Manicavasagar, V, Pan, J, Frith, J. F, Blaszyński A. & Pond C. D. (1996) *Anxiety and depression in general practice patients: prevalence and management. Medical Journal of Australia, 164, 526-9.*

http://www.ccohs.ca/oshanswers/psychosocial/mentalhealth_risk.html

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The Royal College of Psychiatrist (2011) Health Work Wellbeing, www.rcpsych.ac.uk

Spurgeon, P., Mazelan, P., Barwell, F. & Flanagan, H. (2007). *New Directions in Managing Employee Absence: An evidence-based approach*, London: Chartered Institute of Personnel and Development.